

Enabling global location awareness of CAVs via resilient diffusion in Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks

Nikos Piperigkos^{1,2}, Christos Anagnostopoulos^{1,2}, Aris S. Lalos¹
¹Industrial Systems Institute, Athena Research Center, Patras Science Park, Greece
²AviSense.AI, Patras Science Park, Greece
 piperigkos@athenarc.gr, anagnostopoulos@avisense.ai, lalos@athenarc.gr

Abstract—This demo presents the resiliency of our global location awareness approach designed for connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) operating under network delays and GPS inaccurate measurements. For studying thoroughly our method, a realistic traffic and network simulation framework stack has been developed in order to simulate vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANETs). The proposed information diffusion based approach significantly improves the localization accuracy despite the challenging environment, enhancing vehicles’ situational awareness. Our demo is available on: <https://youtu.be/vn6r1g3cQo8>

Index Terms—Localization, awareness, resiliency, diffusion

I. INTRODUCTION

CAVs need to precisely know their locations, in order to efficiently operate. In this context, **GLLME** algorithm [1] has been developed to empower vehicles with global location awareness over a VANET (i.e., localizing all interconnected vehicles), relying on the information diffusion concept and outperforming related SOTA techniques. However, realistic sensing and communication imperfections such as network delays introduced by V2V communication, as well as poor GPS accuracy caused by urban canyons affect algorithm’s performance. In this demo, **GLLME** has been robustified against those challenges and tested within an appropriately deployed simulation framework [2]. The latter consists of CARLA, SUMO and Artery simulators, which through ROS messages generate realistic urban traffic and network conditions for the VANETs (or clusters) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Traffic and network simulator stack.

II. RESILIENT GRAPH LAPLACIAN DIFFUSION

GLLME relies on Graph Laplacian Diffusion, where vehicles exploit the graph Laplacian operator and exchange sensor measurements so as to estimate the positions of all vehicles forming a cluster. However, at the combination step, standard

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Fig. 2: Evaluation metrics include the cumulative distribution function of ego vehicle’s individual location error, as well as the average location error of its cluster. Asynchronous **GLLME-AW** is outperformed by its synchronous counterpart, but still outperforms by 71% and 58% the GPS sensor.

Metropolis rule (considering only cluster topology) underperforms when the received measurements are outdated (due to network delays) or degraded by outliers (due to inaccurate GPS). As such, we will utilize the adaptive weighting rule of [3], in which the measurements transmitted by nearby vehicles are combined if they are not too far from those of ego vehicle. The proposed resilient cooperative localization algorithm is named **GLLME with adaptive weighting (GLLME-AW)**.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Two use-cases have been considered: i) **GLLME-AW** with and without network delay, i.e., asynchronous vs synchronous fusion (Fig. 2), ii) **GLLME-AW** vs **GLLME** in the presence of asynchronous fusion and GPS outliers (**TABLE I**). Overall localization accuracy is very promising and highlights its potential for resilient situational awareness.

TABLE I: Localization accuracy (maximum error) with respect to GPS during the second use-case of demo

	GLLME-AW	GLLME	GPS
Individual location error (<i>m</i>)	8 (-86%)	20 (-66%)	60
Cluster average location error (<i>m</i>)	7.5 (-70%)	11 (-56%)	25

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